

Immediate supervisor's satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas Philippines

Soceline N. Batisla-ong

Iloilo State College of Fisheries-Dingle Campus, Philippines

socelinebatislaong1976@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines are focusing on graduates employability. The immediate supervisors' demand is very high as they look for graduates who are flexible, willingness to learn the job, technically competent, and committed to excellence. Thus, this study was conducted to determine immediate supervisors' satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers produced by one State College in Western Visayas. The descriptive-quantitative research design with a standardized research instruments was employed. Since there were a total of 48 graduates in the year 2002-2019 the researcher decided to take them all as respondents. Frequency count, percentage, and mean were used in the descriptive statistical test and Mann-Whitney and Kruskal Wallis analysis for differences in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction and teachers teaching competence level. Results revealed that respondents' instructional skills, personal and social qualities were rated as "Surpasses Expectations" and "Very Satisfactory" in teaching competence. Moreover, it was found out there is no significant difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction and on the teaching competence of teachers as to program, position, and number of years in teaching. Notably, results exclaimed that one of the college in Western Visayas is producing graduates who are viable to the academic institution where they teach. Furthermore, the school should not remain complacent considering the fast-changing advancement in the educational arena. Thus, the school administration and the dean of the college of education should closely monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of the varied teaching strategies used by teachers ensuring that it enhance students' communication, creativeness, and critical thinking skills.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : Dec. 9, 2021

Revised : April 15, 2022

Accepted : April 17, 2022

KEY WORDS

*Immediate supervisor,
Satisfaction,
Teaching competence,
graduates*

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Batisla-ong, S. (2022). Immediate supervisor's satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 2(1), 63-74. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6496769>

INTRODUCTION

The graduates' employability and performance in the workplace defines the institution's success. Higher education institutions are in charge of developing globally competitive and efficient graduates who have the necessary workplace training. Graduates of higher education should incorporate knowledge, abilities, and attitudes that the modern workplace expected (Winch, 2006). Immediate supervisors, according to Hesketh (2000) wants students to receive rigorous instruction at school that will prepare them for the future job.

There have been ventures into examining employee traits that companies look for, such as Boland and Akridge (2004) and Norwood and Henneberry (2006) in response to the problem of educating students for the world of work. Immediate supervisors, according to Harvey (2000), look for employees who have communication, teamwork, and interpersonal skills. Employees who have access to interactive facts are more likely to communicate effectively (formally and informally). They are comfortable working with individuals from all walks of life, work well in groups, and are adaptable enough to change their duties from one project to the next. Personal qualities and abilities studied by Harvey (2000), include intellect, knowledge, willingness and ability to learn, continual learning, readiness to take chances and demonstrate initiative, self-motivation, self-confidence, and self-management, among others. Institutions of higher education should review the opinions and expectations of immediate supervisors on a regular basis in order to improve the employability of graduates.

The higher education industry has a critical role in improving employability as well as contributing to national economic growth. According to Statistics South Africa (2017), white and Indian demographic groupings had the largest percentage of employed people with a higher education qualification. A tertiary qualification was held by 47.3 percent of the employed white population and 29.7% of the employed Indian population. Employed people with a tertiary education made up only 16.2% and 13.3% of the black and colored populations, respectively. According to statistics from 2015 and 2016, more than half of the employed black and colored people had less than matric education. Furthermore, higher education is responsible for preparing students to be skilled workers who can compete in a diminishing global workforce (Griesel and Parker 2009). "The need for a more seamless interaction between higher education and the workplace" is becoming increasingly apparent in South Africa's higher education industry (Chetty 2012). Institutions of higher learning should review the perspectives and expectations of immediate supervisors on a regular basis in order to improve the employability of graduates. Curriculum planners can use the information gained from these evaluations to connect curricula with critical workplace skills or to launch remedial courses that will improve graduate readiness. Harvey (2000), warns that the academy should not be seen as a "apologist for anti-intellectualism, for the erosion of academic freedom, and as proposing that higher education should be about training graduates for jobs rather than improving their minds" when discussing the relationship between the academy and employment. The new reality for higher education in a globalized world, according to Harvey (2000) is the ability to respond to a quickly changing world is important, but it should not be at the expense of higher education preparation.

In addition, graduates must contribute more than technical knowledge to the job in a knowledge-based economy. Higher education institutions are emphasizing programs that will cultivate and foster skills and qualities, as well as assuring a thorough mastery of subject matter (Yen et.al. 2009). Graduate employability is without a doubt a major concern in today's higher education (Treleaven & Voola, 2008). Therefore, in these perspectives, the researcher opted to conduct this study to determine the immediate supervisor's views on their satisfaction with the quality of the graduates expected of them by their immediate supervisors. This study will also help determine the areas that need improvement to further enhance the teaching competency during their pre-service training workshops and other skills required for the teacher. This study will be beneficial for the school to have a glimpse of the performance of its graduates while providing feedback for curricular evaluation and enhancement. It provides useful insights and input to the development of outcome-based curriculum in coming up with quality education.

Objectives

This study aimed to find out the immediate supervisors' satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers produced by one state college in Western Visayas. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine respondents profile in terms of program, position, and number of years in teaching?
2. Determine the immediate supervisors' satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas when taken as a whole and group according program, position, and number of years in teaching?
3. Determine the teaching competence of teachers according to program, position, and number of years in teaching?
4. Is there significant differences on the immediate supervisors 'satisfaction of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas satisfaction according to program, position, and number of years in teaching?
5. Is there significant differences in the teaching competence of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas when classified according to program, position, and number of years in teaching?

Hypothesis

1. There is significant differences in the immediate supervisors 'satisfaction of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas satisfaction of when classified according to program, position, and number of years in teaching.
2. There significant differences in the teaching competence of teachers product by one state college in Western Visayas when classified according to program, position, and number of years in teaching.

Framework of the study

The immediate supervisors' satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers is an important piece of information that schools must consider to determine the relevance and responsiveness of their curriculum, programs, and services. The paradigm in Figure 1 graphically illustrates the interaction of the variables upon which the present research was anchored.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram showing the variables of the study

METHODS

Research design

A descriptive research design was used in this study to determine the immediate supervisors' satisfaction on teaching competence of teachers produced by one state college in Western Visayas in terms of instructional skills, personal and social qualities, and teaching competence used by the Department of Education. According to Calmorin (2016), this design allows descriptions of the existing phenomenon and comparison of phenomenon or

phenomena among categories of given variables. A quantitative method of research was employed in this study. This method is employed when the objective of this study is answerable by numeric terms or uses numerical data.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were the graduates by one state college in Western Visayas. The institution started in the academic year 2002 were they offered Bachelor of Secondary Education and Bachelor of Elementary Education. Only few students were enrolled from academic year 2002-2019 and employed in the public school. There were 35 Bachelor of Secondary Education and 13 Bachelor of Elementary Education graduates who were responded the survey. Non-probability sampling technique was employed since all the graduates were included as respondents or total enumeration.

Instrument

The research instruments used in this study were adapted from the past studies. The research instrument was divided into three parts. Part I reflected the personal data of the respondents. Part II was a questionnaire checklist on the immediate supervisors' satisfaction adapted from Clavel, et.al (2017) and Part III teaching competence adapted from Palu-ay (2019) used by the Department of Education. The personal data to be filled up by the respondents while the questionnaire checklist on the immediate supervisors satisfaction and teaching competence to be rated by their immediate supervisor.

Data gathering procedure

Since in 2019 this was the first wave of COVID-19 outbreak thus, the researcher tend to administered the research instrument personally to those who live nearby by observing proper health protocols, while those who were far away were sent through e-mail or via Messenger and checked the accomplished instrument as to its completeness. The data collected were tabulated, classified, encoded, statistically processed, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data analysis

In the analysis of data, descriptive and inferential statistical tests were employed in the study. The descriptive statistical tests applied were frequency count, percentage, and mean. In interpreting the mean scores regarding the immediate supervisors' satisfaction level of the respondents taken as an entire group and classified as to variables, the mean scores ranging between 1.00 and 1.49 were regarded as "needs improvement"; those between 1.50 and 2.49 as "meets expectations"; and those between 2.50 and 3.00 as "surpasses expectations". These ranges were obtained dividing them by the number values between 1 and 3, the former being the lowest value assigned to the choices and the latter being the highest. On the other hand, in interpreting the mean scores regarding the teaching competency level of the respondents taken as an entire group and classified as to variables, the mean scores ranging between 1.00 and 1.80 were regarded as "very poor"; those between 1.81 and 2.60 as "poor"; those between 2.61 and 3.40 as "average"; those between 3.41 and 4.20 as "satisfactory"; and those between 4.21 and 5.00 as "very satisfactory". These ranges were also obtained dividing them by the number values between 1 and 5, the former being the lowest value assigned to the choices and the latter being the highest. In variance analysis, in order to determine the groups the significant difference was in favor of, Mann Whitney test was used in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction and teaching competency level when classified into two groups and Kruskal Wallis was used in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction and teaching competency level when classified into three or more groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As reflected in Table, it shows the profile of the respondents in terms of program, position, and number of years in teaching. The respondents are 35 (73%) Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd) and 13 (27%) Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd). The ratio of Bachelor of Secondary Education to Bachelor in Elementary Education is 2:1. Of the 48 respondents, 36 (75%) are Teacher 1, seven (15%) are Teacher 2, one (2%) is Teacher 3, two (4%) are Head Teacher and two (4%) are Master Teacher. The respondents are more of Teacher 1 on the position. Number of years in teaching. Of the 48 respondents, 34 (71%) 5 years and below in service and 14 (29%) 6 years and up in service. Majority of the respondents have rendered five years and below in service.

Table 1 Profile of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Program		
BSEd	35	73
BEEd	13	27
Position		
T1	36	75
T2	7	15
T3	1	2
HT	2	4
MT	2	4
Number of years in teaching		
5 years and below	34	71
6 years up	14	29
As a Whole	48	100

Immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates taken as an entire group

The immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates taken as an entire group in terms of instructional skills and personal and social qualities are reflected in Table 2. The six statements used to determine the instructional skills of the respondents were all rated by their immediate supervisors as surpasses expectations. The respondents' knowledge and mastery of the subject matter taught and preparation of lesson plan got a mean of 2.65, communication skills got 2.56, strategies in the presentation of the lesson and system of classroom routine and discipline 2.63, and efficiency in doing paper works 2.54. The overall mean was 2.61 with an interpretation of "surpasses expectations." The result shows that "knowledge and mastery of the subject matter taught and preparation of lesson plan" ranked number one and the last was "efficiency in doing paper works". This result implies that the graduates were really prepared and competent in terms of their instructional skills. In terms of the efficiency in papers work where it got the lowest mean could be attributed to the bulk of paper works required from them and it changes from time to time. This study is supported with the findings of Yen et.al. (2009) that higher education institutions are emphasizing programs that will cultivate and foster skills and qualities, as well as assuring a thorough mastery of subject matter.

The respondents were also rated by their immediate supervisors in all the five statements as surpasses expectations in their personal and social qualities. In terms of grooming and personality, attendance, and professional ethics they got a mean of 2.81, initiative and resourcefulness 2.79, and involvement in teamwork 2.83. The overall mean was 2.81 or "surpasses expectations." In terms of qualities, "involvement in teamwork" is ranked one and the last is "initiative and resourcefulness." The result implies that graduates could adjust with anybody in their workplace which would lead to harmonious working relationship but slightly lower in terms of "initiative and resourcefulness." According to the study of Azevedo, Apfelthaler & Hurst, (2012); Tsitskari,

Goudas, Tsalouchou & Michalopoulou (2017), states that teamwork is one of the most cited attributes that immediate supervisors look for in their employees. Further, the present study is also supported by Archer & Davison (2008), an employee’s character demonstrated in having a pleasant personality creates the positive atmosphere in the workplace. It is what immediate supervisors are looking for among their employees.

Table 2. Immediate supervisors’ satisfaction

Statement	Mean	Description
Instructional Skills		
-Knowledge and mastery of the subject matter taught.	2.65	Surpasses Expectations
-Communication skills	2.56	Surpasses Expectations
-Preparation of lesson plan	2.65	Surpasses Expectations
-Strategies/Method in the presentation of the lesson and in evaluating student’s performance.	2.63	Surpasses Expectations
-System of classroom routine and discipline.	2.63	Surpasses Expectations
-Efficiency in doing paper works.	2.54	Surpasses Expectations
Sub- Mean	2.61	Surpasses Expectations
Personal and Social Qualities		
-Grooming and personality	2.81	Surpasses Expectations
-Initiative and resourcefulness	2.79	Surpasses Expectations
-Attendance	2.81	Surpasses Expectations
-Professional Ethics	2.81	Surpasses Expectations
-Involvement in teamwork	2.83	Surpasses Expectations
Sub- Mean	2.81	Surpasses Expectations
Grand Mean	2.71	Surpasses Expectations

Legend: 2.50–3.00 (Surpasses Expectations); 1.50–2.49 (Meets Expectations); 1.00–1.49 (Needs Improvement)

Immediate supervisors’ satisfaction of graduates classified as to variables

Table 2a presents the immediate supervisors’ satisfaction of graduates classified as to program, position, and number of years in teaching. The BSEd graduates in terms of instructional skills “surpasses expectations” (M=2.57), and their personal and social qualities also “surpasses expectations” (M=2.82). The BEEd graduates as to instructional skills “surpasses expectations” (M=2.85), and their personal and social qualities also “surpasses expectations” (M=2.80). The respondents according to their position title in terms of instructional skills majority of them “surpasses expectations” Teacher 1(M=2.64), Teacher 2 (M=2.57), Teacher 3 (M=3.00), Head Teacher (M=3.00), and Master Teacher (M=2.50) and also their personal and social qualities “surpasses expectations” Teacher 1(M=2.81), Teacher 2 (M=2.86), Teacher 3 (M=3.00), Head Teacher (M=3.00), and Master Teacher (M=2.50). The instructional skills of the respondents with 5 years and below in service “surpasses their expectations” (M=2.65) as well as their personal and social qualities (M=2.78). The respondents with 6 years and up in service as to instructional skills “surpasses expectations” (M=2.65) and their personal and social qualities also “surpasses expectations” (M=2.90). The result shows that the immediate supervisors’ satisfaction of graduates were all surpassed their expectations. This result implies that regardless of graduates program, position, and number of years in teaching they possess personal and professional qualities required in the teaching profession.

Table 2. Immediate Supervisor’s Satisfaction

Category	N	Mean	Description
Program			
BSEd			
Instructional Skills	35	2.57	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	35	2.82	Surpasses Expectations
BEEd			

Instructional Skills	13	2.85	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	13	2.80	Surpasses Expectations
Position			
Teacher I			
Instructional Skills	36	2.64	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	36	2.81	Surpasses Expectations
Teacher II			
Instructional Skills	7	2.57	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	7	2.86	Surpasses Expectations
Teacher III			
Instructional Skills	1	3.00	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	1	3.00	Surpasses Expectations
Head Teacher			
Instructional Skills	2	3.00	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	2	3.00	Surpasses Expectations
Master Teacher			
Instructional Skills	2	2.50	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	2	2.50	Surpasses Expectations
Number of years in teaching			
5 years and below			
Instructional Skills	34	2.65	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	34	2.78	Surpasses Expectations
6 years up			
Instructional Skills	14	2.64	Surpasses Expectations
Personal & Social Qualities	14	2.90	Surpasses Expectations

Legend: 2.50–3.00 (*Surpasses Expectations*); 1.50–2.49 (*Meets Expectations*); 1.00–1.49 (*Needs Improvement*)

Teachers teaching competence

Table 3 shows the respondents teaching competence of graduates as an entire group. The nine statements used to determine the teaching competence of the respondents were all rated by their immediate supervisors as very satisfactory. The respondents applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas (M=4.60), uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills (M=4.44), applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critically and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills (M=4.48), manages classroom structure to engage learners individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments (M=4.60), manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments (M=4.71), uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences (M=4.63), plans, manages, and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts (M=4.63), selects, develops, organizes and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals (M=4.69), and designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements (M=4.63). The overall mean was 4.60 with an interpretation of “very satisfactory.”

The result shows that “manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments” ranked number one and the last were “uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills”. The results imply that the teacher should provide their learners a range of different contexts in which they can use literacy and numeracy skills. According to United Nations Relief and Works Agency (2013), using various teaching strategies in your class to cater to individual needs is essential when teaching any subject and extending learners' literacy skills. To develop their writing skills, they should encourage learners to compose varied text types- advertisements, announcements, letters, stories, factual texts, and so on, (United Nations Relief and Works Agency, 2013). Furthermore, to strengthen numeracy, the teacher should create a rich and supportive learning environment that will support a

skilful mix of various approaches. It includes active learning and planned, purposeful play, developing problem-solving capabilities, developing mental agility, using technology appropriately and effectively, and promoting interest and enthusiasm for numeracy.

Table 3. Teachers Teaching Competence

Statement	Mean	Description
1.Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	4.60	Very Satisfactory
2.Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	4.44	Very Satisfactory
3.Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critically and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.	4.48	Very Satisfactory
4.Manages classroom structure to engage learners individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	4.60	Very Satisfactory
5.Manages learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	4.71	Very Satisfactory
6.Uses differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners’ gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences.	4.63	Very Satisfactory
7.Plans, manages, and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts.	4.63	Very Satisfactory
8.Selects, develops, organizes and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	4.69	Very Satisfactory
9.Designs, selects, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	4.63	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	4.60	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.21–5.00 (Very Satisfactory); 3.41–4.20 (Satisfactory); 2.61–3.40 (Average) 1.81–2.60 (Poor); 1.00–1.80 (Very Poor)

Teaching competence of graduates classified as to variables

Table 3a presents the teaching competence of graduates classified as to program, position, and number of years in teaching. *Program.* The teaching competence of BSEd “very satisfactory” (M=4.57) and BEEd also “very satisfactory” (M=4.70). *Position.* The respondents according to their position title their teaching competence majority of them were “very satisfactory” Teacher 1(M=4.54), Teacher 2 (M=4.76), Teacher 3 (M=5.00), Head Teacher (M=4.95), and Master Teacher (M=4.56). *Number of years in teaching.* The teaching competence of the respondents with 5 years and below in service “very satisfactory” (M=4.57) as well as the respondents with 6 years up in service (M=4.67). The result implies that the teaching competence of graduates was “very satisfactory” when classified as to program, position, and number of years in teaching. This study means that their immediate supervisors were satisfied as they deliver efficient and effective performance.

Table 3. Teachers teaching competence as to variables

Category	N	Mean	Description
Program			
BSEd	35	4.57	Very Satisfactory
BEEd	13	4.69	Very Satisfactory
Position			

Teacher I	36	4.54	Very Satisfactory
Teacher II	7	4.76	Very Satisfactory
Teacher III	1	5.00	Very Satisfactory
Head Teacher	2	4.95	Very Satisfactory
Master Teacher	2	4.56	Very Satisfactory
Number of years in teaching			
5 and below	34	4.57	Very Satisfactory
6 and up	14	4.67	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.21–5.00 (*Very Satisfactory*); 3.41–4.20 (*Satisfactory*); 2.61–3.40 (*Average*)
1.81–2.60 (*Poor*); 1.00–1.80 (*Very Poor*)

Difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates classified as to variables

Table 4 presents the result of the difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates when grouped according to variables. The result shows that the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates, when classified as to program, was not significantly different as shown by the significance value of 0.399, which is higher than 0.05; both BSEd and BEEd respondents have the same level of satisfaction. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates when classified as to program, was not rejected. When grouped as to the number of years in teaching, the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates did not differ significantly, as supported by a significance value of 0.383, which is higher than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates when classified as to the number of years in teaching, was accepted. This result means that regardless of the number of years rendered, respondents have the same level of satisfaction rated by their employer. The immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates classified as to position when subjected to the Kruskal Wallis resulted in a not significant difference as shown by the significance value of 0.680, which is higher than 0.05. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates when classified as to position, was not rejected. The no significant results mean that regardless of the program, position, and number of years in teaching of the graduates their immediate supervisors satisfaction were comparable. The result implies that program, position, and number of years in teaching did not affect the immediate supervisors' satisfaction level. The study of Thompson et.al (2008), survey showed that over 90 percent of the immediate supervisors look for people who are flexible and adaptive, willing to learn on the job, team players, technically competent and committed to excellence.

Table 4. Mann Whitney and Kruskal Wallis results on the difference in the immediate supervisors' satisfaction of graduates classified as to variables

Variable	Mean Rank	DF	U/X2	V (2-tailed)
Program		1	192.50ns	0.399
BSEd	23.50			
BEEd	27.19			
Number of years in teaching		1	201.00ns	0.383
5 years and below	23.41			
6 years up	27.14			
Position		4	2.31	0.680
Teacher 1	23.46			

Teacher 2	26.43
Teacher 3	38.50
Head Teacher	32.75
Master Teacher	21.25

pns>0.05

Difference in the teaching competence of graduates classified as to variables

As can be gleaned, Table 5 shows the result of the significant difference in the teaching competence of graduates when grouped according to variables. The result shows that the teaching competence of graduates, when classified as to program, was not significantly different as indicated by the significance value of 0.294, which is higher than 0.05; both BSEd and BEEd respondents have the same level of teaching competence. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the teaching competence of graduates when classified as to program, was not rejected. When grouped as to the number of years in teaching, the teaching competence of graduates did not differ significantly, as supported by a significance value of 0.791, higher than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the teaching competence of graduates when classified as to the number of years in teaching, was not rejected. This result means that regardless of the number of years rendered, respondents have the same level of teaching competence. The teaching competence of graduates classified as to position when subjected to the Kruskal Wallis resulted in a not significant difference as shown by the significance value of 0.237, which is higher than 0.05. The null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference in the teaching competence of graduates when classified as to position, was not rejected. Thus, the result shows that regardless of the position of the respondents have the same level of teaching competence. The results mean that irrespective of the graduates program, position, and number of years in teaching their teaching competence were the same. The result implies that the three variables considered in the study were not factors of graduates in teaching competence.

Moreover, competence entails the ability to meet complicated demands by drawing on and mobilizing psychosocial resources (such as skills and attitudes) in a specific setting. In order to achieve excellence as a teacher, you must be competent. To meet the complex difficulties of today's world, teachers require a diverse set of skills. Teaching ability is an essential component of a successful training program aimed at improving the welfare of a certain country or the entire world. In the present study of Shmelev (2002), states that the teaching skills and life-long learning competencies of professional teachers comprise the following: to perform complex pedagogical duties; to be well-spoken, in good mental and physical health, stable and tolerant; to have a propensity to work with the younger generation, good communicative and observational skills, tact, a vivid imagination, and leadership. In addition, student teaching practice in the classroom is the most important component in determining how a student-experience teachers of teacher training is shaped. According to Ludwig, Kirshstein, and Sidana (2010) and Ani, Iketaku, Uzosike (2021) states that teacher training programs have received attention as researchers and practitioners attempt to understand how to best ensure that graduates are equipped to teach all learners and schools can reduce turnover rates.

Table 5. Mann Whitney and Kruskall Wallis results on the difference in the teaching competence of graduates classified as to variables

Variable	Mean Rank	DF	U/X2	V (2-tailed)
Program		1	183.00ns	0.294
BSEd	23.23			

BEEd	27.92			
Number of years in teaching		1	226.50ns	0.791
5 years and below	24.16			
6 years and up	25.32			
Position		4	5.53ns	0.237
Teacher 1	22.40			
Teacher 2	28.50			
Teacher 3	43.00			
Head Teacher	39.25			
Master Teacher	24.25			

Note: $p^* < 0.05$; $pns > 0.05$

CONCLUSION

The results, showing all instructional skills and personal social qualities with surpasses expectations and teaching competence with a very satisfactory rating. Strongly suggest that one of the college in Western Visayas is producing graduates who live up to the expectations from the academe. These findings indicate that the school's rigid training provided to its students is indeed paying off. Hence, the graduates' of the two programs are prepared and knowledgeable of the subjects they handled and could easily adjust in the workplace. They were equipped professionally thru their formal education and various exposures which lead them to perform "very satisfactory". Further, the immediate supervisors' were very satisfied of their performance and teaching competence regardless of their program, position, and number of years in teaching they rendered.

RECOMMENDATION

The implication of this study is for the school to continue looking for ways to sustain and to improve its curriculum, programs, and services to level up in producing efficient and quality graduates with needed instructional skills in the academe. Moreover, the school cannot remain complacent to what it is at the moment so as not to be left behind considering the fast-changing advancement in society. In addition, the administration may call the attention of the Dean of the School of Education to monitor the varied teaching strategies used by the faculty regularly and evaluate their effectiveness. The professors may encourage the Education students to use the Speech Laboratory to further improve their communication skills. The Dean may require the faculty to emphasize efficiency in doing paper works with the application of the latest technology. The professors may expose the students in an activity where they could further develop their initiative and resourcefulness. Lastly, the professors may use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learners' achievement in literacy, numeracy skills, develop critical, and creative thinking. The researcher further recommend to validate the results of the present investigation.

REFERENCES

- Ani, M.I., Iketaku, I.R. & Uzosike, P.C. (2021). Mentoring in teacher education: An experience that makes a difference for college of education student teachers. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 1(1), 26-34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5195604>
- Azevedo, A., Omerzel, D.G., Andrews, J., Higson, H., Caballero, A. & Frech, B. (2012). Satisfaction with knowledge and competencies: A multi-country study of immediate supervisors and business graduates.

- American Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 4(1), 23-39. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/1324964651?accountid=37714>
- Boland, M.A. & J.T. Akridge. 2004. Undergraduate agribusiness programs: Focus or alter? *Rev. Agric. Econ.* 26:564–589
- Calmorin, L.P. (2016). *Research and Thesis Writing with Statistics Computer Application*. Manila: Rex Book Store
- Clavel, R.P., Aghon, D.C., & Garrido, G.B. (2017). Immediate supervisors' Feedback of the Education Graduates: *Teacher Education Research Journal*. Vol.6, No.1.ISSN#2244-3630
- Dela Fuente, J.A. (2019). Driving Forces of Students' Choice in Specializing Science: A Science Education Context in the Philippines Perspective. *The Normal Lights*, 13(2), 225 – 250.
- Dela Fuente, J.A. (2021). Implementing inclusive education in the Philippines: College teacher experiences with deaf students. *Issues in Educational Research*, 31(1), 94-110.
- Harvey, L. 2000. New realities: The relationship between higher education and employment. *Tertiary Education and Management*. <https://qualityresearchinternational.com/essectools/relatedpubs/New%20Realities.pdf>
- Hesketh, A.J. (2000). Recruiting an elite? Immediate supervisors' perceptions of graduate education and training. *Journal of Education and Work*, 13, 245-271. <https://doi:10.1080/713676992>.
- Ludwig, M., Kirshstein, R. & Sidana, A. (2010). An Emerging Picture of Teacher Preparation Pipeline. Paper Presented at the Annual Conference of the American Association of Colleges for Teacher Education, Washington, DC.
- Norwood, F.B. & S.R. Henneberry. (2006). Show me the money! The value of college graduate attributes as stated by immediate supervisors and perceived by students. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 88:484– 498.
- Shmelev, A.G. (2002). *Psychodiagnosis of personnel characteristics*. Saint-Peterburg.
- Statistics South Africa.(2017). Quarterly labour force survey: Quarter 1: 2016: Statistics South Africa. <http://www.statssa.gov.za/publications/PO211stQuarter2016.pdf>
- Thompson D., Treleaven L., Kamvounias P., Beem B. & Hill E., (2008). Integrating Graduates Attributes with Assessment Criteria in Business Education: Using an Online Assessment System, *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practise*, Vol. 5/1.
- United Nations Relief and Works Agency. (2013). School Based Teacher Development Programme Transforming classroom practices. <https://www.unrwa.org/sbtd>
- Winch, C. (2006). Graduate attributes and changing conceptions. In *Graduate attributes, learning, and employability*, ed. P. Hager and S. Holland, 67–89. Dordrecht: Springer.
- Yen, P. et.al., (2009). Immediate supervisors Feedback on Business Graduates: An Exploratory Study in Curtin Sarawak. *International Review of Business Research*.